

Fishing Architecture

From Fish to Commodity. London's Billingsgate Market as Connector between Terrestrial and Marine Landscapes

André Tavares^a

With the collaboration of Alice Nouvet^a

Magazine Article, May, 2024 MA24.03 V1

This text is an abridged version of a passage from *Architecture Follows Fish. An Amphibious History of the North Atlantic*, forthcoming at The MIT Press in October 2024.

Published in a+u, no. 643, May 2024, Tokyo, p. 52-55.

Before a saltwater fish ends up on our plate, it swims in the sea. As London's urban population swelled, so-called "wet" fish became a widely available, but expensive, alternative to cured fish. London's Billingsgate market, a capital location for the fish trade, is a revealing construction of architecture's role in the fish's path from animal to food. The building catered London's fish urban logistics until its replacement by new facilities in 1982, when the wholesale market was moved east to Canary Wharf and the historic market building was converted to an office space by Richard Rogers. To a certain extent, his architectural qualities reflected its ever-growing ecological impact on fish populations up to the North Sea. The fish market condensed both the centripetal and centrifugal forces propelled by the combined effect of urban growth, railways, and trawling.

Billingsgate was a loud, frenzied area flavored by the odor of fish, with barges docked at piers that were extensions of city streets. The concentration of the city's fish trade in a single location puzzled many contemporary chroniclers. But that concentration made sense given that the product was fresh fish. Fish supply is more unpredictable than other food items. Variables such as seasonal trends, meteorological and navigational conditions, and the behavior of fish made the fresh fish trade a highly specialized niche with volatile prices. As a result, buying at the wholesale market required expert knowledge that discouraged direct trade between individuals or households and sellers. Instead, fish bought

Figure 1 — Horace Jones, Billingsgate Market, London, 1877

wholesale at Billingsgate was distributed to retailers in neighborhoods throughout the metropolis.

Market halls of the nineteenth century like Billingsgate's replaced outdoor market squares. As Nikolaus Pevsner noted, the new buildings were a curious hybrid of the railway station and the exhibition hall of an international fair. Before the 1850s, when a proper market hall designed by James Bunning (1802–1863) was erected, fish were sold on rather informal constructions. In 1842, Charles Knight (1791–1873) wrote an atmospheric description of Billingsgate, dominated by the presence of fog and boats moored on the Thames: "The boats lie considerably below the level of the market, and the descent is by several ladders to a floating wharf, which rises and falls with the tide, and is therefore always on the same level as the boats." Fish would soon arrive by rail in increasing numbers. With the help of the extensive British railway system and the telegraph that allowed traders to ascertain the best deals throughout the distribution network, markets were connected to different fisheries, and London became the center

of fish consumption, offering a combination of species harvested in various geographic locations.

The first Billingsgate market building opened in August 1852. Designed by city architect James Bunning, it was an ingenious machine. The market's most prominent feature was the clock tower facing the river, the main purpose of which was ventilation. The mechanical system used "revolving pump-discs" to drain "the air from the lower vaults and market by suction, and propel it up the air-shaft enclosed within the clock-tower; by which contrivance it is said that 50,000 cubic feet of contaminated air can be expelled in a minute." The water needed "for washing fish, washing hands, washing the market, and keeping everything neat and clean" was pumped directly from the Thames.

The new architecture was a result of new diet habits. Describing the London "of the poor" in 1851, Henry Mayhew emphasizes the role of railways, "by means of which fish can be sent from the coast to the capital with much greater rapidity, and therefore be received much fresher than was formerly the case" and the resulting transformation of fresh fish from an expensive product

Figure 3 — London’s area supplied from Billingsgate, 1958. Sourced from James Bird, *A Central Metropolitan Market*, 1958.

to a low-cost commodity: “This cheap food, through the agency of the costermongers, is conveyed to every poor man’s door, both in the thickly-crowded streets where the poor reside—a family at least in a room.” The selection of available fish reflected the diversity of marine resources conveyed to London. From the Atlantic waters of Cornwall to the North Sea harbors of Lincolnshire and Norfolk, such variety called for different prices and propelled new consumption habits. It was within this context that fried fish came to be Britain’s most popular takeaway food in the twentieth century. Already in

1851 Mayhew counted between 250 and 350 fried-fish sellers in the vicinity of Billingsgate, transforming portions of sole and plaice into “shapeless brown lumps of fish.” Fish was chopped into indistinguishable chunks, battered with flour, and deep fried, which allowed it to be preserved and sold by street sellers distributing cheap food in poor neighborhoods. The working class now had access to a cheap, ready-made, and protein-rich food. It was a perfect match between an uneven supply and a strong demand, and it soon defined entire city areas by the smell alone.

Business at Billingsgate boomed so quickly that in 1877, just twenty-five years after the opening of the modern market hall, it had to be replaced by a larger building. This new market, still standing today, was designed by Horace Jones. The open central hall is roofed by an ingenious scheme of top-lit iron roof trusses that contrast with the more discrete load-bearing brick walls of the surrounding market galleries. Billingsgate's distinctive working hours began at five o'clock in the morning, and by nine, the main business had been concluded. Several illustrations of the market interior show large oil lamps hovering over the stands, breaking through the obscurity of dawn by the Thames.

With a new consumer culture came new ecological pressure. The growth of urban fish markets in the middle of the nineteenth century, facilitated by railway transport, was sustained by an increase in trawling and the development of new trawling technologies. The expansion of fish markets in the 1850s came with the exploitation of the rich fishing grounds of the North Sea, with fishing fleets moving further and further from the main harbors of Hull and Grimsby. Several new technologies transformed the business. The introduction of the mechanical capstan to wooden boats (relieving from the hard effort of hauling a loaded trawl), steam power (granting the boat independence in the face of variable winds), and steel-hulled vessels, transformed the 20 to 30 tons wooden sailing boats into 70 to 80 tons powerful trawling machines. The new vessels could take larger hauls over longer periods far from their landing harbor. Connected to London by rail, Grimsby and Hull were the harbors that best represented this "trawling revolution," a change made possible by significant growth in the urban demand for fish. From the perspective of fish, architecture is a passage. Appearing on its path from animal to commodity, London's Billingsgate market is an interface, a construction inscribed within a sequence of logistical movements leading from fish harvesting to their arrival in distant places to be turned into food.

History (London: Sampson Low, Marston, 1935).

5 Construction begun in 1874, and the market opened on July 20, 1877.

6 Bunning's most acclaimed building was the Coal Exchange, inaugurated in 1849, with a prominent cast-iron dome.

7 George Dood, *The Food of London* (London: Longman, Brown, Green and Longmans, 1856), 347.

8 Henry Mayhew, *London Labour and the London of the Poor: The Condition and Earnings of Those That Will Work, Cannot Work, and Will Not Work* (1851; London: Charles Griffin and Company, 1864), 64, 173–176.

9 John K. Walton, *Fish & Chips and the British Working Class, 1870–1940* (London: Leicester University Press, 1992); Panikos Panayi, *Fish and Chips. A Takeaway History* (London: Reaktion Books, 2014).

10 Callum Roberts, *The Unnatural History of the Sea: The Past and the Future of Humanity and Fishing* (London: Gaia, 2007), 146.

1 Nikolaus Pevsner, *A History of Building Types* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1976), 235–256.

2 Charles Knight, ed., *London* (London: Charles Knight & Co., 1843), 4:193–208.

3 Knight, *London*, 4:202.

4 James Bird, "Billingsgate: A Central Metropolitan Market," *The Geographical Journal* 124, no. 4 (December 1958): 468. See also William John Passingham, *London's Markets: Their Origin and*

Fishing Architecture
Centro de Estudos de Arquitectura e Urbanismo
Faculdade de Arquitectura da Universidade do Porto
Via Panorâmica Edgar Cardoso, n.º 215
4150-564 Porto

ceau@arq.up.pt
www.fishingarchitecture.com

European Research Council
Established by the European Commission

FISH-A Funded by ERC-CoG2022 101044244
— European Commission, Horizon Europe

Fishing Architecture is a research project funded by the European Union (ERC, Fish-A, 101044244). The views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

